

Metalated Graphyne-Based Networks as 2D Materials: Crystallization, Topological Defects, Delocalized Electronic States and Site-Specific Doping

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ABSTRACT

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7 Graphyne-based 2D carbon allotropes feature extraordinary physical properties;
8 however, their synthesis as crystalline single layered materials has remained challenging.
9 We report on the fabrication of large-area organometallic Ag-*bis*-acetylide networks and
10 their structural and electronic properties on Ag(111) using low-temperature scanning
11 tunneling microscopy combined with density functional theory (DFT) calculations. The
12 metalated graphyne-based networks are robust at room temperature and assembled in a
13 bottom-up approach *via* surface-assisted dehalogenative homocoupling of terminal
14 alkynyl bromides. Large-area networks of several hundred nanometers with topological
15 defects at domain boundaries are obtained due to the Ag-acetylide bonds' reversible
16 nature. The thermodynamically controlled growth mechanism is explained through the
17 direct observation of intermediates, which differ on Ag(111) and Au(111). Scanning
18 tunneling spectroscopy resolved unoccupied states delocalized across the network. The
19 energy of these states can be shifted locally by attachment of a different number of Br
20 atoms within the network. DFT revealed that free-standing organometallic-*bis*-acetylide
21 networks are semimetals with linear band dispersion around several high-symmetry
22 points, which suggest the presence of Weyl points. These results demonstrate that the
23 organometallic Ag-*bis*-acetylide networks resemble the typical 2D material characters,
24 which makes them of great interest for fundamental studies and electronic materials in
25 devices.
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44 KEYWORDS: two-dimensional materials, graphyne-based carbon allotropes,
45 crystallization, topological defects, doping effect, Dirac-cone materials
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4 Two-dimensional carbon allotropes¹⁻⁵ have been one of the major paradigms in
5 chemistry and material science since the discovery of graphene.⁶ More recently,
6 graphyne- and graphdiyne-based materials consisting of sp^2 - and sp -hybridized carbon
7 atoms attracted significant interest because of their extraordinary electronic properties
8 predicted by density functional theory (DFT) calculations.⁷⁻¹¹ However, the synthesis of
9 single-layered crystalline graphyne by conventional solution-based chemistry is elusive.¹²
10 Therefore, considerable efforts have been made towards the bottom-up fabrication of
11 graphyne- and graphdiyne-based structures through various coupling reaction schemes
12 on metal surfaces.^{13,14} So far, most of the on-surface synthesis studies of graphyne- and
13 graphdiyne-based structures have been limited to dimers,¹⁵ macrocycles,¹⁶ and extended
14 wires¹⁷⁻²² by using acetylenic precursors. The on-surface synthesis of extended graphyne
15 and graphdiyne networks remains challenging due to the limited control of the alkyne
16 coupling reactions on metals that frequently leads to the formation of undesired side-
17 products. In addition, the irreversibility of the covalent C-C bond formation precludes the
18 networks from self-ordering.^{18,23}

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20 Recently, alkynyl-metal networks featuring metal-*bis*-acetylide $C\equiv C-M-C\equiv C$ bonds were
21 proposed as interesting graphyne-based 2D materials due to their intriguing electronic
22 properties.^{24,25} DFT suggested that Au-*bis*-acetylide networks are magnetic 2D organic
23 topological insulators with half-metallic character.^{24,25} Scanning tunneling spectroscopy
24 (STS) experiments confirmed the covalent nature of $C\equiv C-Ag-C\equiv C$ bonds,²⁶ which
25 represents an essential ingredient for the hypothesized 2D organic topological insulators.
26 We note, a $C\equiv C-Ag-C\equiv C$ or $C\equiv C-Au-C\equiv C$ linkage with its covalent character is drastically
27 different from non-covalent coordination interactions commonly observed in Au cyanides
28 with $CN\cdots Au\cdots CN$ bonding.²⁶⁻³⁰

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30 Experimentally, bromoacetylenes facilitate the formation of metal-*bis*-acetylide
31 structures as intermediates after cleavage of the Br atoms on Ag and Au surfaces at room
32 temperature.^{26,31} These organometallic networks transform after chemical conversion
33 partially into C-C coupled patches and form graphdiyne-based networks.³¹ However, the
34 formation of large-area organometallic Au-*bis*-acetylide networks proved difficult on
35 Au(111), because they are reaction intermediates.³¹ Ag(111) exhibits a weaker molecule-
36 surface interaction due to a weaker interaction of the alkynes with Ag metal atoms^{23,32}

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4 and has shown to be suitable for the fabrication of large-scale and complex
5 organometallic Ag-*bis*-acetylide networks.^{26,33,34} In general, the surface chemistry, growth
6 mechanism, and electronic properties of metal-*bis*-acetylide networks on metal surfaces
7 are so far not well studied and hence the suitability of the metal-*bis*-acetylide networks
8 for application as 2D materials remained unexplored.
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12 Here, we demonstrate that Ag-*bis*-acetylide graphyne-based networks resemble typical
13 2D material properties using scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) combined with DFT
14 calculations. We report on the crystallization in large area domains, the formation of
15 topological defects at domain boundaries, the high degree of π -conjugation *via*
16 delocalized unoccupied electronic states across the network and the site-specific doping
17 through the attachment of adsorbed Br. The robust organometallic graphyne-based
18 networks are fabricated by dehalogenative homocoupling reactions of 1,3,5-tris(2-
19 bromoethynyl)-benzene (Br-TEB) on Ag(111), see Scheme 1. The thermodynamically
20 controlled growth mechanism is rationalized through the direct observation of
21 intermediates, which differ on Ag(111) and Au(111). In addition, DFT calculations reveal
22 that the free-standing metallic-*bis*-acetylide networks are semimetals with linear band
23 dispersion at Γ in the case of Ag and along ΓK and ΓM for Au. This suggests the presence
24 of Weyl points; an in-depth analysis of these points, however, is beyond the scope of this
25 work.
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Scheme 1. Chemical structure of the Br-TEB and the formation of metal-*bis*-acetylide networks at room temperature on the Au(111) and Ag(111) surface. Upon deposition at room temperature, the Br terminal groups are cleaved, and the molecular radicals bind to native metal adatoms on the surface. Subsequent annealing at 470 K leads partially to covalently linked C≡C-C≡C bonds on Au(111). In contrast, the covalent C-C linkage is mostly prohibited on Ag(111) at these conditions, which results in the crystallization of the organometallic network.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

On-surface assembly and structure of Ag-*bis*-acetylide networks. 1,3,5-tris(2-bromoethynyl)-benzene (Br-TEB) is used as the reaction precursor for the fabrication of metal-*bis*-acetylide networks *via* dehalogenative homocoupling, see Scheme 1. The reaction proceeds similarly as recently reported on Au(111).³¹ However, there is evidence for different intermediates on Au(111) and Ag(111), which strongly affect the structural quality of the 2D layers and will be discussed in the following.

Figure 1. Structure of the organometallic Ag-*bis*-acetylide networks formed *via* dehalogenative homocoupling of Br-TEB molecules on Ag(111) at room temperature. (a) Overview and (b) close-up STM images of the organometallic networks on Ag(111) ($U = 0.3$ V, $I = 50$ pA). (c) STM image of one pore ($U = 1.8$ V, $I = 30$ pA) with the bonding model overlaid (red circles: Ag atoms). (d) Zoomed-in STM image ($U = 0.3$ V, $I = 50$ pA) of the bonding structure at the edge of an island. White arrows highlight terminal alkynyl moieties that are not saturated by adatoms and might bind towards substrate atoms.

We previously showed that Br-TEB remains intact upon sub-monolayer deposition at 90 K and self-assembles in islands with an X_6 -synthon structure on Au(111).³⁵ Here, we discuss the dissociative adsorption on Ag(111) at 300 K, where all three terminal Br groups are cleaved from the molecule leaving three unsaturated carbons with one unpaired electron each. The missing valence of the carbon is compensated by bonding to metal adatoms. The latter are naturally present on the surface in the form of defects or extracted from the surface layer *via* diffusion and ligand extraction (Figure S1).³⁶⁻³⁸ Figure 1 shows STM images of the self-assembled honeycomb networks after the deposition of Br-TEB on the Ag(111) surface held at 300 K, with the TEB backbones located at the corners of the hexagons. Cleaved Br atoms are found next to the networks on the bare metal surface (occasional protrusions in the bottom of Figure 1a) and in the network's pores. The TEB backbones are connected by Ag adatoms that have a higher

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4 apparent height in STM images.³⁹ We compared the measured center-to-center distance
5 of two adjacent molecules (1.22 ± 0.03 nm) with plausible structures determined by DFT
6 (see Table S1), which confirmed an excellent agreement with the Ag-atom-linked dimer
7 featuring the $C\equiv C-Ag-C\equiv C$ bonding motif. Therefore, we can conclude that the observed
8 honeycomb networks are organometallic Ag-*bis*-acetylide scaffolds with the bonding
9 model shown in Figure 1c. Figure 1d shows that the pores at the island edges are closed,
10 which occasionally results in 5-membered pores. Interestingly, the third acetylenic group
11 of TEB molecules at the edge of the island, which can contribute only two Ag-*bis*-acetylide
12 bonds to the network, are not saturated by adatoms and can bind towards the surface
13 atoms. The observed depressions support surface bonds in the STM image²⁸ and are
14 highlighted with the white arrows in Figure 1d.
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24 **Thermal-activated crystallization and topological defects.** Kinetic constraints on the self-
25 assembly at room temperature yield small domain sizes (around 20 nm) of the
26 honeycomb networks due to a randomly inserted second denser phase within the
27 honeycomb network (Figure 2a). In addition, some hexagonal pores are distorted and
28 also non-six-membered polygons are observed, as shown in Figure 2b. The detailed STM
29 image in Figure 2e reveals that the denser domains consist of parallel molecular dimers
30 with Ag-*bis*-acetylide bonds. These dimers might be stabilized by additional metal- π
31 interactions between Ag adatoms and the alkyne moieties, as known from crystal
32 engineering.⁴⁰
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Figure 2. Crystallization of the organometallic networks on Ag(111). (a) Large overview and (b) close-up STM images of the honeycomb network upon deposition of Br-TEB at 300 K. Extended organometallic networks are inhibited by a second compact phase that is randomly inserted within the honeycomb networks. (c-h) Overview and zoomed-in STM images after subsequent annealing to 470 K feature extended honeycomb networks: (c) Extended honeycomb networks connect through point defects (blue oval) and line defects (green rectangles) while the dense phase is separated; (e) Zoomed-in STM image and the bonding model of the second compact phase; (f-g) Bias-dependent STM images (drift corrected) with a Br functionalized. At 0.5 V (f) the molecular triangle points towards the Ag atoms and the residual Br atoms are visible as round protrusions, while at 1.8 V (g) the molecular triangles appear 180° rotated and Br is challenging to identify. (h) STM image of the honeycomb network measured at room temperature (RT). STM parameters: (a,b) $U = 1$ V, $I = 50$ pA, (c,d) $U = 1.8$ V, $I = 300$ pA, (e,f) $U = 0.5$ V, $I = 300$ pA, (g) $U = 1.8$ V, $I = 300$ pA, (h) $U = 1.8$ V, $I = 5$ pA.

The domain size and crystallinity of the *Ag-bis*-acetylide networks are significantly improved by post-annealing to 470 K. The large domain size of the networks is achieved by a phase separation of the honeycomb from the denser dimer structures, as shown in Figure 2c. The long-range ordered networks can extend over several hundred nanometers, only limited by the terrace size of the metal substrate. Furthermore, the distortion of the hexagonal pores is self-corrected by the thermal activation to a large

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3 extent (Figure 2d-g), which demonstrates the dynamic and reversible character of the
4 organometallic $C\equiv C-Ag-C\equiv C$ bonding motif. Hence, a thermodynamically controlled
5 crystallization of the organometallic graphyne-based honeycomb networks is achieved.
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7 The networks represent a compromise between the desired bonding strength for
8 robustness and error correction *via* bond reversibility for ordering. Importantly, we
9 demonstrate the robustness of the organometallic honeycomb networks at room
10 temperature. The STM image in Figure 2h is recorded at 300 K and proves the room
11 temperature stability of the organometallic networks, which is a crucial requirement for
12 their potential application in electronic and sensor devices. Subsequent annealing to 500
13 K causes the decomposition and desorption of the Ag-TEB networks on Ag(111)
14 (Figure S2) and only a few C-C coupled dimers were observed near defects (Figure S3).
15 In summary, Ag(111) facilitates the crystallization of Ag-*bis*-acetylide networks upon
16 annealing. Therefore, we assume that the organometallic Ag-*bis*-acetylide networks are
17 not metastable reaction intermediates, but thermodynamically stable products before
18 desorption is induced by further annealing.

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20 The STM topography of the network and the Br atoms are bias-dependent, as shown
21 in the STM images measured by a Br-functionalized tip in Figure 2f-g. At 0.5 V, the
22 molecular triangle points towards the Ag atoms and the residual Br atoms are visible as
23 round protrusions, while at 1.8 V the molecular triangles appear 180° rotated and Br is
24 difficult to see. It is interesting to note that the cleaved Br atoms attach to the TEB
25 backbones and the Ag adatom of the networks (Figure 2f).

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27 In order to get more in-depth insights into the crystallization mechanism of the metal-
28 *bis*-acetylide networks and the influence of the molecule-surface interaction, we compare
29 the structure formation of the honeycomb networks from Br-TEB molecules on the
30 Au(111) surface. The hexagonal networks, formed at room temperature, have a similar
31 structure (Figure 3a) and also small domain sizes of defect-free areas. Post-annealing to
32 470 K does not improve the ordering of the networks (Figure 3c); instead, some of the
33 Au-acetylide bonds transform into C-C bonds by releasing the Au atoms, which causes
34 local stress in the network (Figure 3d). Subsequent annealing to 580 K leads to the
35 formation of small patches of graphdiyne structures (Figure S2) as previously reported in
36 Ref. [31]. We can conclude that the metal-*bis*-acetylide bond can cleave on both surfaces
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4 at 470 K; however, the C-C coupling reaction on Au has a lower activation barrier and
5 proceeds at lower temperatures. Therefore, the organometallic Au-*bis*-acetylide
6 structures on Au(111) are mainly reaction intermediates for the C-C coupling, while on
7 Ag(111) a thermodynamic control of the Ag-*bis*-acetylide structures is achieved. These
8 significant differences in the on-surface reaction of Br-TEB on Ag(111) can be rationalized
9 by carefully inspecting the metal-acetylide bond strength and geometry as well as the
10 effect of the Br.
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16 Our DFT calculations in gas phase revealed that the Au-TEB bond is about 0.38 eV
17 stronger than the Ag-TEB bond, see Table S1. In contrast, the experimentally observed
18 reaction barrier for the C-C coupling is lower on Au(111) than on Ag(111). Hence, the
19 temperature window for the reversible bond formation and breaking in the metal-*bis*-
20 acetylide networks is larger on Ag(111). This microscopic reversibility of the metal-*bis*-
21 acetylide is crucial for the error-correction in self-assembled honeycomb networks. The
22 higher onset for C-C coupling on Ag(111) might be related to an unfavorable bonding
23 geometry, which is identified by our STM data. Figure 1d shows that the alkynyl units at
24 the edge of the islands on Ag(111) are not saturated by adatoms and can bind towards
25 surface atoms supported by the observed depressions on the STM image and leaving the
26 network closed at the border. In contrast, as depicted in Figure 3b, the alkynyl ligands
27 bind to Au adatoms on the Au(111) surface, leading to protrusions in the STM image and
28 facilitating an open network at the edge. Hence we assume, when the organometallic
29 bonds break due to thermal activation, the unsaturated ligands bend downwards on
30 Ag(111) but stay "straight" and horizontal with respect to the Au(111) surface. DFT
31 calculations demonstrate that for on-surface Glaser-type coupling, the bond to the
32 substrate is not a good starting point,^{41,42} the more "straight" geometry with the adatoms
33 is, therefore, more suitable. The different bond geometry is, on the one hand, a result of
34 the lower formation energy of Au adatoms than Ag,^{37,38} which leads to more Au adatoms
35 available for bonding than the Ag case. On the other hand, the different coordination
36 chemistry on the surface stabilizes linear metal-acetylide bonds only in metal-*bis*-
37 acetylide complexes on Ag(111) in contrast to Au(111), where both metal-acetylide and
38 metal-*bis*-acetylide complexes are linear.
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Figure 3. Organometallic networks on Au(111). (a) STM image ($U = 0.5$ V, $I = 50$ pA) upon deposition of **Br-TEB** on Au(111) at room temperature. (b) close-up ($U = 0.5$ V, $I = 180$ pA) STM image of the bonding structure at the edge of an island. White arrows highlight terminal alkynyl moieties that bond towards Au adatoms. (c) STM image ($U = 0.5$ V, $I = 300$ pA) after post-annealing the sample in (a) to 470 K. (d) Zoomed-in STM image ($U = 0.5$ V, $I = 30$ pA) showing the onset of covalent C-C bond formation. The white arrows highlight C=C-C \equiv C bonds.

Moreover, both the molecule-surface interaction and the interaction with the Br influences the on-surface reaction of TEB. TEB is expected to have a higher adsorption energy on Au(111): DFT calculations demonstrated that the Au(111) surface has a stronger interaction with the phenyl than Ag(111),^{23,37,43} and there is the same trend for the interaction between alkyne with Au(111) and Ag(111).²³ Experimentally, we observed several rotational domains of TEB on the Ag(111) compared to only one on Au(111), see Figure S4. This indicates a weaker surface interaction of **TEB** on Ag(111) and lower

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4 desorption temperature of the organic ligand on Ag(111). The lower desorption
5 temperature might compete with the formation of C-C bonds during annealing.
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8 In our high-resolution STM images, we can unambiguously identify the adsorption sites
9 of the cleaved bromines in the honeycomb networks. Both on Au and Ag, we see that Br
10 can interact with the TEB backbone and the metal adatoms (Figure 3b and Figure 2f). We
11 note that the later might influence the reaction barrier for the cleavage of metal-acetylide
12 bonds. Furthermore, the cleaved bromines on Au(111) affect the herringbone
13 reconstruction. The herringbone reconstruction is distorted and avoids the regions
14 covered by molecules (Figure S4c).⁴⁴ The confinement of the metal-*bis*-acetylide
15 networks between the distorted herringbone reconstruction presumably hinders the
16 growth of extended islands.
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23 In summary, our experimental data provides a detailed picture of the on-surface
24 reaction mechanism of TEB: the bent bond geometry on Ag(111) compensates the
25 weaker Ag-TEB bond strength, hence, induces a high energy barrier for further C-C
26 coupling, thereby stabilizing the Ag-*bis*-acetylide networks as the chemically and
27 thermally stable product of the on-surface reaction of Br-TEB on Ag(111). In contrast, the
28 lower barrier for the C-C coupling reaction on Au(111) has the consequence that the
29 organometallic Au-*bis*-acetylide structures are mainly metastable reaction intermediates
30 for the C-C coupling.
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Figure 4. Topological defects in the organometallic networks on Ag(111). Detailed STM images of networks with (a)-(b) 5-7-7-5 point defects ($U = 0.5$ V, $I = 300$ pA) and (d)-(e) 5-5-8 line defects ($U = 1.8$ V, $I = 300$ pA) after annealing at 470 K. (c) and (f) show the structural models of the point and line defects, respectively, color code: carbon gray, silver yellow, hydrogen white. The STM images in this figure are recorded with Br-functionalized tips to visualize the Ag atoms better. The bias voltage in (a)-(b) leads to a reorientation of the TEB-backbone-derived triangles in the STM image and the residual Br atoms are well resolved compared to (d)-(e) (see also Figure 2f-g).

An interesting effect of the crystallization is the formation of characteristic topological defects at domain boundaries (Figure 2c). Different domains of the honeycomb networks are connected through point defects (Figure 4a) and one-dimensional line defects (Figure 4d). The point defects are Stone-Thrower-Wales (STW) defects,⁴⁵ where four hexagons are converted into pentagon-heptagon pairs (designated as 5-7-7-5 point defects, Figure 4b). This type of defect is found to generally exist in covalently-bonded 2D materials with honeycomb structure, for example, in graphene created by electron activation with TEM⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ and in silica and germania films driven by thermal activation.^{49,50} Interestingly, the STW defects here tend to expand and form one-dimensional line defects. In addition, well-defined line defects, consisting of alternating pentagon pairs and octagons (referred to as

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4 5-5-8 line defects), are formed in the organometallic graphdiyne-like networks. As shown
5 in Figure 4e, this type of defect is essentially a degenerate grain boundary, *i.e.*, a
6 translation of two half-lattices with zero misorientation angle relative to one another.
7 Similar 5-5-8 line defects have also been observed in graphene,^{51,52} oxide glass films,
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Similar 5-5-8 line defects have also been observed in graphene,^{51,52} oxide glass films,
49,50 two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides,⁵³ and in surface-supported ice
layers,⁵⁴ but so far, to our knowledge, not in organometallic networks.^{55,56} In fact,
topological defects facilitate the growth of large-scale materials by avoiding the presence
of rotational domains. This offers an alternative method to gas-mediated surface reaction
for synthesizing large-domain organometallic films.³³ Moreover, topological defects
represent a particularly efficient tool to tune the physical and electronic properties of
graphene-based materials.⁴⁸ The structural similarity in our organometallic *Ag-bis*-
acetylide networks with those in graphene offers fascinating perspectives for controlled
defect engineering in two-dimensional organometallic materials.

Notably, many defects exist in the *Au-bis*-acetylide networks; however, no well-defined
defect structures are formed (Figure S5). It is plausible to conclude that the 5-7-7-5 point
defects and 5-5-8 line defect structures in the *Ag-bis*-acetylide networks are facilitated by
the relatively weak interaction with the underlying substrate.

Delocalized states and linear band dispersion of the metal-*bis*-acetylide networks. The
long-range ordered organometallic *Ag-bis*-acetylide networks are chemically and
thermally stable. These exciting properties make them attractive organic two-dimensional
materials for application in electronic devices. We note that the Ag atoms form a kagome
lattice and the organic molecules a hexagonal lattice in these honeycomb networks. Both
lattices typically yield band structures with Dirac cones. Hence, we discuss their electronic
structure next.

Figure 5. Electronic properties of the organometallic networks. (a) dI/dV spectra (set point: -1 V, 50 pA) recorded across the TEb-Ag-TEb bridge as indicated in (b). The orange spectrum is measured at the center of one pore and reveals the confined surface state of Ag(111). The spectra are vertically shifted for clarity. (b) STM image ($U = 1.0$ V, $I = 300$ pA) and (c) the corresponding dI/dV map recorded around S1 state ($U = 1.0$ V). (d) Calculated spin-polarized band structures by DFT (PBE+D3) of the Ag-*bis*-acetylide and Au-*bis*-acetylide networks in gas phase. The blue (red) lines show the spin-up (spin-down) bands. The bottom graphs highlight the bands around the Fermi level.

Figure 5a shows the dI/dV spectra recorded across a TEb-Ag-TEb bridge (marked in Figure 5b). The Ag(111) surface state below the honeycomb network (labeled as SS) is shifted above the Fermi level to 100 meV caused by the increase of the work function upon the adsorption of TEb. In the center of the pores, the surface state is observed at around 400 meV (orange-colored curve in Figure 5a) due to confinement effects.^{57,58} Besides the shifted surface state, two resonant states are resolved at the TEb backbone in the unoccupied region: state 1 (S1) at ~ 0.85 eV and state 2 (S2) at ~ 1.6 eV. Both states

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4 also exhibit intensities at the Ag atom. The state S1 is delocalized across the network, as
5 revealed by corresponding STS maps in Figure 5c. The delocalization of electronic states
6 is a sign of covalent bonding and a high degree of π -conjugation.²⁶⁻²⁹ Indeed, the *Ag-bis*-
7 acetylide shows much stronger bond strength than the typical metal-organic coordination
8 interactions attributed to the involvement of the unpaired electron from the C atom.²⁶

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11 In order to explore the origin of the states in the STS, we calculated the band structure
12 of the *Ag-bis*-acetylide network by DFT. The calculations were performed for the free-
13 standing network, which should supply sufficient information owing to its physisorption on
14 the surface. As shown in the left panel of Figure 5d, the network is semimetallic with three
15 empty bands within 0.4 eV of the Fermi level. CB and CB+2 bands of the other spin
16 channel are localized above 3 eV with contribution from the carbon atoms. The energy
17 difference between the CB and CB+2 bands at Γ is around 0.5 eV, which is comparable
18 with the measured energy difference between the S1 and S2 states. Therefore, we assign
19 the S1 and S2 states in the STS to the CB+1 and CB+2 bands, respectively, (CB and
20 CB+1 are degenerate at Γ). This means that the bands are shifted down around 2 eV
21 upon adsorption of the network on the metal surface, which is similar to Ag-TET
22 networks.²⁶ Consequently, the CB band is localized at -2 eV and fully occupied, in
23 agreement with the fact that it cannot be accessed in the STS above -1 eV. The
24 comparison of the measured data on the surface with the calculated results in gas phase
25 reveals the influence of the Ag(111) surface on the electronic properties of the *Ag-bis*-
26 acetylide network. The metal surface transfers electrons to the network as an electron
27 donor, which is accompanied by a shift of all the bands downwards in energy by
28 approximately 2 eV with respect to the Fermi level to make the CB band fully occupied
29 and enhance the state mixing between C and Ag to facilitate the delocalization of the
30 states.²⁶

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33 The DFT calculated band structure shows some other interesting features of the
34 organometallic networks. Both π_{\parallel} and π_{\perp} bands show Dirac-cone-like crossings with
35 linear band dispersion around each K point (Figure 5d), which is typical for two-
36 dimensional kagome and hexagonal lattices. More importantly, a candidate for a Weyl
37 point, i.e., a point of linear bands crossing, is observed in the spin down channel at the Γ
38 point.

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4 We also calculated the band structure of *Au-bis*-acetylide network (right panel of Figure
5 5d) to study the effect of changing the metal linker from Ag to Au atoms. First, the
6 unoccupied bands with π_{\perp} character around 3 eV are shifted downwards by around
7 0.2 eV in the case of Au. This is due to the increased band dispersion in combination with
8 a lowering of the bottom flat band. Second, the dispersionless metal d band located
9 around -1 eV in case of Ag is shifted downwards for Au, below the π_{\perp} bands. This leads
10 to a significant change in the dispersion of the latter, as they are now shifted upwards
11 even further, crossing the CB. As a result, two crossings of linear bands are observed at
12 the Fermi level, suggesting Weyl points on the paths along ΓK and ΓM . The overall
13 electronic structure of the Au-TEB networks agrees well with previous reports on their
14 magnetic topological properties.²⁵

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16 Since we showed that the effect of the Ag(111) substrate was a mere shift of the band
17 structure (n -doping) in the Ag-TET case, it is expected that the results and insights gained
18 for the Ag-TEB and Au-TEB networks in vacuum are also transferable to the substrate
19 supported cases, taking into account an additional n -doping effect by the respective
20 substrate. Both are promising candidates for organic topological insulators, which
21 however requires an electronic decoupling from the substrate.²⁵

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Figure 6. The p -doping effect of Br atoms to the organometallic networks. (a) dI/dV spectra at TEBA backbones attached with one (cyan), two (olive), and three (red) Br atoms (set point: $-1V$, 300 pA) as indicated in (b). The S1 state shifts upwards with an increasing number of Br atoms attached to a molecule. In addition, the spectra at the bare Ag(111) surface and the pore are also shown. (b) An STM image ($U = 0.3\text{ V}$, $I = 300\text{ pA}$) and its corresponding dI/dV maps (c-d) were recorded around S1 and S2 states, respectively. The colored triangles indicate the number of attached Br.

In the Ag-TEBA network, the pores are frequently decorated with residual Br atoms that interact with H atoms of the benzene ring and the metal adatom (Figure 2f). We therefore carefully measured the impact of the residual Br on the electronic structure of the TEBA-based network. In Figure 6a, the STS spectra show a stepwise upshift of the CB+1 (S1) and CB+2 (S2) energies related to the attachment of an increasing number of Br atoms to the TEBA backbone (see Figure 6b). This is consistent with Br acting as an electron acceptor leading to a p -doping effect on the graphene predicted by DFT calculations⁵⁹ and measured for polymeric wires with angle-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy.⁶⁰ Here, we report the atom-number-dependent p -doping effect of Br in single-molecule resolution by utilizing the spatially resolved STM technique. As shown in the dI/dV maps

(Figure 6c-d), the TEB backbones exhibit different contrasts at specific energies, indicating the high sensitivity of the electronic structure towards single adsorbates. This offers a strategy to locally tune the electronic structure within the networks.

CONCLUSIONS

We have studied the thermodynamically controlled growth, the associated topological defect engineering as well as the electronic properties of two-dimensional organometallic graphdiyne-like networks fabricated on Ag(111) by using Br-substituted triethynyl-derivatives as molecular precursors. In contrast to previous studies on Au(111), where Au-acetylide structures were only observed as reaction intermediates,³¹ the organometallic networks with the C≡C-Ag-C≡C bonding motif on Ag(111) are chemically stable also at room temperature and are not observed to transform into C-C coupled polymers at 470 K due to higher activation barriers. We conclude from our high-resolution STM data that the different reaction behaviors are induced by the different bond geometry after C≡C-Metal-C≡C bond scissions. The reversible character of the organometallic bonds yields large crystalline domains upon post-annealing by phase separation and introduces point and line defects at domain boundaries, which allows for controlled defect engineering. Such ordered defects have, to our knowledge, not been achieved previously in two-dimensional organometallic networks.⁵⁶ The crystallization is the prerequisite to promote the evolution of a defined band structure for a material. The STS resolved two states at the unoccupied region that are assigned as the CB+1 and CB+2 bands shifted down by the *n*-doping effect of the Ag(111) surface. The DFT calculations demonstrate that the resulting graphdiyne-like networks are semimetals with linear band dispersion around several high-symmetry points, which suggest the presence of Weyl points. In comparison to graphene or C-C bound networks, the acetylide bound network are intrinsically *n*-doped by the incorporated metal linkers, which, in principle, should allow for excellent charge carrier transport without further modification. Furthermore, the onset of the states energies can be locally tuned within the networks by attachment of different number of Br atoms that act as electron acceptor and lead to *p*-doping. To conclude, the

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3 organometallic Ag-*bis*-acetylide networks feature the typical 2D material properties, which
4 makes them of great interest for fundamental studies and future applications.
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8 9 METHODS

10 **Experiment.** The experiments were performed with a commercial low-temperature
11 STM (Scienta Omicron GmbH) operated in ultra-high vacuum (base pressure below 1×10^{-10}
12 mbar). The Ag(111) surface was cleaned *in-situ* by repeated cycles of Ar⁺ sputtering
13 and annealing at 750 K. Br-TEB molecules were evaporated onto the metal substrates
14 kept at room temperature (RT) from a commercial Knudsen cell (Kentax GmbH) with the
15 quartz crucibles held at 300 K. The molecules were thoroughly degassed prior deposition
16 on the surface. The indicated bias voltages refer to the sample bias, although the tip was
17 biased and the sample electronically grounded during the STM measurements. All the
18 STM topographic images were acquired in constant current mode at 4.4 K (except
19 Figure 2d) and processed with Nanotec WSxM⁶¹ software. The dI/dV spectra and maps
20 were measured with a lock-in amplifier with a modulation amplitude of 10 mV (root mean
21 square) and a frequency of 721.99 Hz. The feedback loop was open while recording
22 individual dI/dV spectra. When moving the tip from one point to another in line spectra,
23 the feedback loop was closed, thereby keeping the tip-sample distance constant. The
24 dI/dV maps were recorded in constant current mode so that the effect of the different
25 adsorption heights between TEB backbones and the Ag atoms can be minimized. 1,3,5-
26 Tris(2-bromoethynyl)-benzene (Br-TEB) were synthesized from known 1,3,5-
27 triethynylbenzene⁶² through bromination with *N*-bromosuccinimide.
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42 **Theory.** Open shell DFT calculations were carried out with the Vienna *ab Initio*
43 simulation package⁶³ employing a plane wave basis set up to a kinetic energy threshold
44 of 415 eV and the projector-augmented wave method⁶⁴ for the description of core
45 electrons. The applied Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof exchange-correlation functional⁶⁵ was
46 supplemented with the D3 correction⁶⁶ (including Becke-Johnson damping)⁶⁷ to account
47 for dispersive interactions. Self-consistent field cycles and geometry optimizations were
48 converged to 10^{-6} eV and until forces acting on ions were below 0.005 eV/Å, respectively.
49 Free-standing systems in vacuum were computed with a space of 15 Å separating
50 periodic mirror images in the *z*-direction. A smearing width of 0.05 eV was used to
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3 evaluate the density of states of the networks. To account for the finite size of the slab
4 model, a dipole correction⁶⁸ was employed into *z*-direction. Reciprocal space was
5 sampled using a $3 \times 3 \times 1$ Monkhorst-Pack grid.⁶⁹
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12 ASSOCIATED CONTENT

13 **Supporting Information**

14 The Supporting Information is available free of charge.

15 Additional STM data on the metal adatoms source for forming the metalated networks
16 (**Figure S1**), the temperature dependence of the networks on Ag(111) and Au(111)
17 (**Figure S2-3**), the interaction between the networks and the substrates (**Figure S4**) and
18 the defects in *Au-bis*-acetylide networks on Au(111) (**Figure S5**).
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27 The authors declare no competing financial interest.
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TOC Figure

